

Data Archiving after Project Completion

When it comes to storing, archiving and publishing research data, misunderstandings often arise due to unclear definitions and inconsistent usage of these terms by different service providers. For example, many repositories refer to “archiving” or even “long-term storage” of data, yet only retain data for a duration of 5 to 20 years.

To ensure clear communication, the Research Data Management Network of the University of Basel has defined the terms as follows:

Term	Description	Provider	Time
Active storage	Active data management in a filing system within a running research project	IT-Services , sciCORE , SWITCHdrive	1-5 years
Mid-term storage/ deposition/deep storage	Finalized data(sets), to be reused for further (internal) projects	sciCORE : deep storage	1-10 years
Publication	Curated and disseminated (selected) data(sets), understandable and reusable for others	Repositories	5-20 years
Preservation, (long-term) archiving	Highly valuable data and digital objects to be kept forever (e.g. cultural heritage data, singular data such as climate data)	University Library (only for cultural heritage data)	100+ years

How long do I have to keep my data after the end of a project?

- The University of Basel requires its researchers to keep the data for at least 5 years. ([Regulation relating to academic integrity at the University of Basel, Art. 4, 8](#)).
- The SNSF recommends a retention period of at least 10 years. ([FAQ Preservation and long-term storage of research data](#)).
- All data relating to clinical trials must be retained for at least 20 years after completion or premature termination of the clinical trial ([Ordinance on Clinical Trials, ClinO, Art. 45](#)).

In certain cases, retaining data for the long-term is advisable. Long-term archiving involves addressing key challenges related to preserving digital materials, including format obsolescence, media degradation, and evolving technologies.

Evaluating data for long-term archiving:

Long-term archiving is not suitable for all types of data. The following considerations can help guide the evaluation process.

Reasons for long-term archiving:

- The data holds significant value and potential future importance for researchers and society.
- The data is unique and irreplaceable (e.g. weather observations or interviews with contemporary witnesses).
- The data has not yet been fully explored or analyzed scientifically.

Long-term archiving is not recommended for data from standard procedures or measurement results that can easily and inexpensively be reproduced as needed.

